

FULL FIELD STRAIN MEASUREMENT OF BRAIDED COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

Braided composites consist of continuous fibers embedded in a matrix. Braid mechanical properties are influenced through selection of matrix and fibers and by modifying the braid manufacturing process. Control of braiding parameters allows for tailorable mechanical properties. The objective of this work is to utilize full-field strain measurement approaches for the assessment of braided composite structures. Two full-field strain measurement methods will be utilized (1) Three Dimensional Digital Image Correlation- 3D DIC and (2) Digital Volume Correlation-DVC. 3D DIC is an optical stereo camera based strain measurement method while DVC is an x-ray based tomographic approach that allows for volumetric strain measurement. The two correlation methods utilized in this study provide both surface and volumetric strain data for braided composite structures. The approaches outlined in this work are a critical first step towards better understanding the internal and external deformation and strains that occur within braided composite structures and results will be used towards analytical and numerical models for braided composites.

1 INTRODUCTION

Braided composites consist of woven fibers imbedded in a matrix to form a composite structure [1]. Two dimensional (2D) braided composites are manufactured using Maypole or radial braiding machines. The mechanical properties of braided composites can be manipulated through control of the braiding process parameters, such as braiding angle, and selection of constituent materials. Two-dimensional braided composites are manufactured in Diamond (1/1), Regular (2/2), Hercules (3/3), and Triaxial (1/1 or 2/2 + axial yarns) configurations as shown in Figure 1 [1]. By the nature of the manufacturing process, braided composites offer highly customizable mechanical properties. Unlike conventional composite structures, braided composites exhibit interwoven yarns which present a challenge for the measurement, analysis, and modeling. To model the mechanical behavior, braided composites feature a structure known as a unit cell (Figure 1) which repeating feature that is commonly used to represent the entire braid structure.

Strain of braided composites is commonly measured using conventional strain measurement devices like extensometers or strain gauges [2]. Naik *et al.* used Moiré interferometry to first visualize strain fields in braided composites [3]. This work demonstrated the variations in strain that exist due to the interwoven structure of braids. Periodic strain fields were observed due to the repeating unit cells within the braid structure. Due to the non-uniform nature of textile and braided composite structures it is recommended that strain gauges be selected to be equal to greater in size that the repeating unit cell [4]. Analysis of braided structures is further complicated by deformation that occurs to braid yarns during loading [5]. Braided composites also exhibit progressive failure which includes matrix failure, delamination, and fiber failure [6], [7]. Due to these challenges, alternative evaluation methods are required to evaluate the behavior of braided composite structures.

Figure 1: Representative braiding patterns and unit cell used to represent braided structures

Full-field strain measurement methods have recently become the primary evaluation technique for assessing strain [8]. Two dimensional (2D) and three dimensional (3D) imaging techniques have been utilized to evaluate the external strain of braided structures [9]–[17]. X-ray based measurement methods have also been used to assess the geometry and void content of braided composite structures [18]–[20]. However, limited volumetric strain measurement of braided composites have been performed.

The objective of this work is to examine full-field strain measurement methods for the assessment of braided composite structures. Two full-field strain measurement methods will be utilized (1) Three Dimensional Digital Image Correlation (3D DIC) [21] and (2) Digital Volume Correlation (DVC) [22]. 3D DIC is a stereo camera optical strain measurement method while DVC utilizes X-ray computed tomography for strain measurement. Braided composites have been assessed under uniaxial tension as well as torsion to assess the resultant strain fields [17]. Both methods will allow for the visualization and measurement of the full field strain. The two correlation methods utilized in this study provide both surface and volumetric strain data for braided composites. Both internal and external strain needs to be assessed to fully characterize the mechanical behavior of braided composite structures. Approaches, such as the Virtual Field Method, can be used in conjunction with full-field strain data for constitutive model development [23]. The approaches outlined in this work are a critical step towards building a complete dataset for improved understanding the internal and external deformation and strains that occur within braided composite structures and results will be used towards the development of analytical and numerical models for braided composites.

2 METHODS

2.1 Braid Composite Manufacturing

Braid preforms were manufactured from BioMid fibers (BioMid Fiber, 1650 Denier, Burnaby, BC) using a 36 carrier Maypole braiding machine (Steeger USA, K80-72, Steeger USA, Inman, SC). Braid preforms were manufactured in a Regular (2/2) configuration. The preforms were impregnated with a bio-based two-part epoxy resin (Super Sap® ONE/ONF System, Entropy Resins, Inc., Bay City, MI) using 9.525 mm (3/8”) diameter mandrels.

2.2 3D DIC Strain Braided Composites

Braid samples were evaluated under tension, torsion and 3-point bending tests to observe their strain fields these loading conditions. The 3D DIC testing setups are shown in Figure 2. Strain throughout the surface of braided structures vary following the braid pattern. To capture the variation of strain along the surface the 3D DIC measurement method was used during the mechanical tests.

Figure 2: Experimental loading conditions for braided composite structures for 3D DIC analysis (a) tension (b) bending (c) torsion

For the tensile and torsional 3D DIC tests braid samples were collected with a pair of high resolution cameras (AVT GT3400, Allied Vision Technologies, Stadtroda, Germany). The cameras were each equipped with 35-mm camera lenses (LM35SC, Kowa Optical Projects Co., Tokyo, Japan) and extension tubes (CML5, Thor Labs, Newton, NJ). The imaging equipment used in this study was selected to provide a field of view of approximately 39.3 x 29.4 mm². For the 3-point bending 3D DIC setup, two high resolution cameras (LaVision Imager M-lite 5M, LaVision GmbH, Göttingen, Germany) were used with a resolution of 2464 x 2056 pixels with 10 mm extension tubes (CML10, Thorlabs Inc., Newton, NJ) and 50 mm focal length lenses (NMV-50M23, Navitar, Inc., Rochester, NY), with an f-number of f/16. The imaging setup resulted in a field of view of 46.02 x 38.36 mm². The camera setups were selected to maximize the braid sample within the field of view.

A commercial software package was used to process images of the braid samples acquired during bending tests (DaVis version 10.0.3 StrainMaster, LaVision GmbH, Göttingen, Germany). Subsets of 31 x 31 pixels were used at a step size of 10 pixels to correlate features between consecutive images. The measurement details for the three experimental configurations is detailed in Table 1. Strain field results for the tubular braid samples were post-processed using a custom visualization script (MATLAB 2019a, MathWorks, Natick, Mass.) which made use of the PIVMat toolbox (PIVMat Toolbox 4.10).

Table 1: Braided composite 3D DIC imaging and correlation parameters

Digital Image Correlation Parameters	Tension/ Torsion	3-point bending
Camera Resolution (pixels)	3384 x 2704	2464 x 2056
Camera Pixel Size (μm)	3.69	3.45
Camera Lenses	2X Kowa 35mm lens with 5mm extension tubes	2X Navitar 50mm lens with 10mm extension tube
Camera Field of View (mm ²)	39.3 x 29.4	46.02 x 38.36
Image Scale Factor (pixels/mm)	85.88	53.67
Correlation Subset Size	31 x 31 pixels	31 x 31 pixels
Correlation Step Size	10 pixels	10 pixels
Image Acquisition Rate	1 Hz	4 Hz

2.4 DVC Strain Measurement Braided Composites

The braided composite sample were evaluated using a μCT measurement device (SkyScan 1272, Bruker, Belgium). A compressive load was applied to the samples using an integrated testing stage (424 N Integrated Test Stage, MTS2, Bruker, Belgium). The braid sample was cut to a length of 20.0 mm to allow for compressive loading within the material testing stage. The braid sample was loaded in axial

compression as shown in Figure 3 with a load of 250N. The scanning parameters used to examine the tubular braid sample are detailed in Table 2. The scanning parameters were selected to maximize the braid sample within the field of view and to ensure sufficient contrast for the DVC analysis methods. Two x-ray image data sets were collected. First a reference dataset prior to mechanical testing was collected followed by a second dataset was collected while the compressive load was applied to the braid sample.

Figure 3: Experimental loading conditions for DVC analysis of tubular braided composites

Table 2: Micro-computed tomography (μ CT) scan parameters

μ CT Parameter	Value
X-Ray Voltage	40 kV
Current	200 μ A
Frame Averaging	2
Rotation Step	0.3°
Number of Projections	642
Image Resolution	4904 x 3280 pixels
Projection Exposure Time	529 ms
Detector Pixel Size	7.4 μ m
Reconstructed Image Pixel Size	3.0 μ m

A series of projections of the braided sample were collected for each load step. The projections were loaded into reconstruction software (NRECON 1.7.1.0, Bruker, Belgium) to obtain a series of cross-sectional images of the braided composite. To achieve correlation from image x-ray tomographs a contrast pattern is required. The contrast pattern can be achieved with natural features such as variations in resin and fiber density within a test sample. An example contrast pattern for a braided composite sample is shown in Figure 4. In this figure variations in contrast can be seen between the matrix and fibers within the braid cross-section. The braid contrast pattern is demonstrated by plotting grayscale contrast against position as shown in this figure. The inherent contrast pattern will be utilized for volume correlation between the two x-ray datasets.

Volumetric strain fields for the braided composite sample were obtained using an open-source software package (FIDVC) using a desktop workstation (Precision T5600, Dell, Round Rock, Texas) [22]. The workstation was equipped with 128gb of RAM and a dual core processor (E5-2670 2.60 GHz processor, Intel, Santa Clara, California). The correlation parameters utilized to examine the braid sample are detailed in Table 3. Once the displacement vector field is computed, Lagrangian strain is found using the open source MATLAB script (LD-3D-TFM, version 1.1) [24].

Table 3: Digital Volume Correlation processing parameters

DVC Parameters	Value
Initial Correlation Subset Size (pixels)	128x128x128
Final Correlation Subset Size (pixels)	32x32x32
Mesh Size (pixels)	20
Processing Time (h)	15

Figure 4: Example contrast pattern within a braided composite sample

3 RESULTS

3.1 3D DIC Strain Results

Representative strain fields for tubular braided composites are shown in Figure 5. Results from tension, torsion, and 3-point bending loads are demonstrated in this figure. For each loading condition, three strain fields are displayed longitudinal (ϵ_{xx}) transverse (ϵ_{yy}) and in-plane shear (γ_{xy}). Figure 5 (a)-(c) shows the resulting strain fields for the braid sample under tensile loading. Figure 5 (d)-(f) shows the resulting strain fields for the braid sample subjected to torsional loading. Figure 5 (g)–(i) shows the resulting strain fields for the braid sample under 3-point bending. This figure demonstrates the capability of the 3D DIC measurement method to visualize and quantify the behavior of braided structures due to three different loading conditions. Additionally, in each of the shown images multiple braid unit cells can be examined. The effect of each loading condition on the resulting strain field can be also observed.

Figure 5: Representative strain fields for tubular braided composites (a) tensile loading transverse strain ϵ_{xx} (b) tensile loading longitudinal strain ϵ_{yy} (c) tensile loading in-plane shear γ_{xy} (d) torsional loading longitudinal strain ϵ_{xx} (e) torsional strain transverse strain ϵ_{yy} (f) torsional loading in-plane shear γ_{xy} (g) 3-point bending loading longitudinal strain ϵ_{xx} (h) 3-point bending loading transverse strain ϵ_{yy} (i) 3-point bending loading in-plane shear γ_{xy} .

3.2 DVC Strain Results

Representative strain fields for the tubular braided composite sample obtained from the DVC measurement method will be visualized using three planes within the braid sample. The braid geometry shown in Figure 6 (a) was created from the μ CT image dataset in order to visualize the 3D braid geometry. The three strain visualization planes for the tubular braid sample are shown in Figure 6 (b). This figure shows the Front, Right, and Top visualization planes with respect to the reconstructed braid geometry.

Figure 6: Reconstructed braided composite geometry from μ CT data (a) Resultant 3D geometry (b) Top, Front, and Right strain visualization planes

The resultant displacement magnitude obtained using the DVC measurement method of the tubular braid sample is shown in Figure 7. In this figure the displacement magnitude in the Front, Right and Top visualization planes of the braid sample are shown. This figure shows that translation of the braid sample occurred during testing. Variations in displacement within the braid samples can be observed in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Displacement magnitude for a tubular braid sample under compressive loading (a) Frontal plane (b) Right plane (c) top plane

Volumetric strain of the tubular braid sample was visualized using the three viewing planes (Front, Right, and Top) described in Figure 6. The resulting strain fields for ϵ_{xx} , ϵ_{yy} , and ϵ_{zz} are shown in Figure 8 (a)-(i). The images in Figure 8 show the resulting strain fields that develop in the x , y , and z directions for the braid sample. To represent the volumetric strain of the tubular braid, sample Von Mises Equivalent strain was computed using equation (1) using the six independent components of strain obtained from the DVC analysis process. An equivalent strain was utilized for visualization of the braid strain data to simplify the number of strain fields required for visualization and analysis. The resultant Von Mises Equivalent Strain fields for the tubular braid sample are shown in Figure 8 (j)-(l). In this figure, variations in the internal strain of the tubular braid sample can be observed. Localized strain field variations shown in Figure 8 are the result of internal defects and voids within the braided structure. Additionally, the strain field variations due to the applied compressive load can be seen for the tubular braid sample.

$$\epsilon = \begin{bmatrix} \epsilon_{xx} & \tau_{xy} & \tau_{xz} \\ \tau_{yx} & \epsilon_{yy} & \tau_{yz} \\ \tau_{zx} & \tau_{zy} & \epsilon_{zz} \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

$$\epsilon_{eq} = \frac{2}{3} \sqrt{\frac{3(\epsilon_{xx}^2 + \epsilon_{yy}^2 + \epsilon_{zz}^2)}{2} + \frac{3(\tau_{xy}^2 + \tau_{yz}^2 + \tau_{zx}^2)}{4}}$$

Figure 8: Resultant strain fields for a tubular braid sample under compressive loading. Three viewing planes are used to represent strain within the braid sample (Front, Right and Top) (a)-(c)

Strain ϵ_{xx} (d)-(f) Strain ϵ_{yy} (g)-(i) ϵ_{zz} (j)-(l) Von Mises Strain

4 DISCUSSION

In this work, two full field strain measurement methods have been used to assess braided composite

structures. Full field techniques are necessary to assess the non-homogeneous interwoven structure of braided composites. The 3D DIC measurement method is an effective approach to measure surface strains. Example strain fields obtained for tensile, torsional and 3-point bending loadings are demonstrated in Figure 5. The strain fields shown in Figure 5 demonstrate the adaptability of the 3D DIC measurement method to a variety of loading conditions. The 3D DIC method can be readily adapted for a range of braid geometries and length scales.

Despite the versatility of the 3D DIC measurement method, only external surface strains can be quantified. Alternative methods are necessary to examine the internal strain within braided composites and to further investigate the interaction of the yarns that make up the braided structure. A major challenge that exists in the modeling and analysis of braided composite structures is the interface between yarns. A number of finite element analysis (FEA) models have been developed for braided structures however experimental investigation of the interface between braid yarns and strain within braid yarns has not been investigated [25]–[27].

The DVC measurement approach allows for measurement of the internal strain fields of braided composite structures. The results shown in Figure 8 demonstrate that internal strain within a tubular braid can be obtained using this analysis technique. Applying the DVC approach to braided structures is critical for examining the strain at the interface between braiding yarns; investigate strain within individual yarns; and examine the effect of voids within braided structures. The DVC method has been used for laminated and woven composite structures however; no DVC measurement data exists for braided composite structures [28], [29]. DVC measurements will allow for improved understanding of the interaction between braid yarns within the composite structure. Optimization of the μ CT analysis and DVC measurement of braided composite structures is necessary. Further work is required to determine the optimal μ CT voxel size, DVC correlation voxel size for braided composite structures.

5 CONCLUSIONS

In this work tubular braided composites were examined in four different loading conditions: tension, torsion, 3-point bending, and lateral compression. To evaluate the braided structures full field strain measurement techniques were utilized. Braided structures were examined using both 3D DIC and DVC measurement methods. Full field strain measurement methods are necessary to examine braided composite structures. Due to the interwoven nature, braided composites exhibit non-uniform deformation and strain. 3D DIC is effective for examining surface strain of braided structures. Volumetric strain measurement allows for the strain within individual braid yarns to be examined. Yarn interaction within braided composite can be examined using the DVC volumetric strain measurement method. Both full field methods are necessary approaches for characterization of braided structures.

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